

D1.8 - MOVING Practice Abstracts

First set

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Introduction

MOVING Practice Abstracts (PA) aim at communicating easy to access information to practitioners relevant to the project.

The main objective of this deliverable D1.8 MOVING Practice Abstracts (first set) is to provide: 1) key results and outcomes of specific tasks that have been carried out so far in MOVING; and 2) main practical recommendation(s) to enable the practitioners make use of the results.

This document overviews a total of 31 Practice Abstracts¹ based focus on the following topics:

- Value Chain Analysis in the 23 mountain reference regions
- Participatory Theory Building
- Inventory of Mountain Value Chains
- Farming and Forestry Systems in Mountain Areas
- Farming and Forestry Systems Susceptibility to Climate Change
- Mapping of mountain areas vulnerability
- Tools for Science-Society-Policy Interfaces
- Creating a Community of Practice on Mountain Areas
- Participatory Value Chain Analysis - Methodology

All Practice Abstracts developed by MOVING will be available on the EIP-AGRI database and also published on the MOVING website in the Library section and Reference Regions pages.

→ <https://www.moving-h2020.eu/library/>

→ <https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference-regions/>

They will be communicated and disseminated through the various MOVING channels, including social media, newsletter, blog, etc.

¹ A native language version is included for some of them.

1. The strength of cooperation: sheep farmers cooperative in the region of Weiz

Sheep farming has a long tradition in Austrian mountainous areas in order to graze the steep areas, and to gain meat, milk and wool, but after WW2 sheep products continuously lost relevance. Some farmers from the region of Weiz joined forces in the 1970s to foster a revival of sheep farming against the trend of cattle that traditionally graze the mountain pastures in this region. Like in other parts of Austria, sheep husbandry is practiced on an extreme small scale - only 25 sheep in average. This makes the processing and marketing of the sheep products very time-consuming for the single farm, direct sale is not very attractive. On the other hand, single farms do not have the capacity to supply to retailers, and they

have a weak position in price negotiations. Thus a cooperative was founded, which established its own brand for premium lamb, dairy products and recently cosmetics from whey as well. The cooperative uses the LEADER programme since 25 years on the one hand to develop further, but on the other hand also to achieve an optimal embedding in the regional development. It runs its own dairy with meat processing facilities and a shop, it is shareholder of the local slaughterhouse, and organises the marketing and sale of all food products and cosmetics, and organises educational programmes. Only the marketing of wool is not covered. Nearly all value chain activities take place within the region, and the products are sold regionally or at most in the province of Styria through various channels ranging from direct sale at the cooperative's shop, to farm shops, small local retailers, gastronomy, supermarkets and e-commerce. The cooperative does not only create favourable framework conditions for the farmers, but also sets the basis for continuous high quality and sustainable growth.

MOVING Reference Region
Austrian Alps
Country Austria
Authors Sandra Karner, David Steinwender and Jürgen Suschek-Berger (IFZ)
More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/austrian-alps-austria/

Native language

Gemeinsam erfolgreich: Die Genossenschaft der Weizer Schafbauern

In den 1970er schlossen sich einige Landwirte aus der Region Weiz zusammen, um die Schafhaltung gegen den Trend der traditionellen Almbewirtschaftung mit Rindern wiederzubeleben. Schafzucht in Österreich ist extrem klein strukturiert: im Durchschnitt werden nur 25 Muttertiere pro Betrieb gehalten. In solchen Strukturen gestaltet sich die Verarbeitung und Vermarktung der Schafprodukte für die einzelnen Höfe sehr aufwändig, was eine Direktvermarktung unattraktiv macht. Andererseits fehlen kleinen Betrieben die nötigen Kapazitäten, um den Handel zu beliefern, und sie befinden sich in Preisverhandlungen meist im Hintertreffen. Durch die Gründung einer Genossenschaft konnte eine eigene Marke für Premium-Lammfleisch, Milchprodukte und neuerdings auch Kosmetika aus Molke etabliert werden. Die Genossenschaft nutzt das LEADER-Programm seit 25 Jahren, um sich als Organisation weiter zu entwickeln und eine optimale Einbettung in die Regionalentwicklung zu erreichen. Derzeit wird eine eigene Molkerei mit Schaukäserei, Fleischverarbeitungsinfrastruktur und einem Geschäft betrieben. Zudem ist die Genossenschaft Gesellschafterin des örtlichen Schlachthofs, sie organisiert die Vermarktung und den Verkauf und organisiert Bildungsprogramme. Lediglich die Vermarktung von Wolle ist ausgenommen. Nahezu alle Aktivitäten der Wertschöpfungskette finden in der Region statt. Der Großteil der Produkte wird regional vermarktet. Die Vermarktung erfolgt über verschiedene Kanäle, beginnend beim Genossenschaftsladen, über Hofläden, kleine Nahversorger, die regionale Gastronomie, bis hin zu Online-Vermarktung und Supermarktfilialen. Die Genossenschaft schafft nicht nur günstige Rahmenbedingungen für die Landwirt*innen, sondern auch für nachhaltiges Wachstum.

2. Overcoming the challenges of public policy-making for maintaining the supply of public goods from High Nature Value (HNV) farmland in Bulgaria

The Western Stara Planina (WSP) region of Bulgaria is one of 23 mountain value chain case studies in the H2020 MOVING project (<https://www.moving-h2020.eu/>). It is characterised by low input extensive agriculture and the majority of farmland in the region is considered as High Nature Value (HNV). Over many years, traditional farming practices have created and maintained a diverse range of semi-natural habitats for valuable plant and animal species, many of which are protected by international conventions.

Well-designed public policies, especially EU-funded rural development measures, have great potential to reduce the loss of HNV farmland in the WSP and to maintain the supply of biodiversity-related public goods. For example, HNV grasslands were eligible for agri-environmental payments under the 2007-2013 and 2014-2020 Bulgarian Rural Development Programmes. Nonetheless, the supply of these public goods continues to be at risk due to various factors and much greater attention needs to be given to more integrated and innovative approaches that address the profitability and overall socio-economic viability of the traditional HNV farming systems in the region.

This is a complex task for Bulgarian policymakers. Effective interventions must be designed, targeted and implemented to ensure complementarity, coherence and consistency around common objectives. Wide consultation with relevant stakeholders is therefore essential, as is the “watchdog” role of civil society organisations such as the Society for Territorial and Environmental Prosperity (STEP).

For more information see: <https://www.step-bg.bg/en> and <https://www.arc2020.eu/bulgarias-cap-strategic-plan-backsliding-on-nature-and-biodiversity/>

MOVING Reference Region
Stara Planina
Country Bulgaria
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More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/stara-planina-bulgaria/

3. Beef production in Šumava mountains

Extensive cattle breeding and beef production is a traditional and widespread method of land use in the Šumava mountains. Like other regions, Šumava is also affected by global climate change, which is affecting agricultural production there. These are the main reasons for choosing the beef production value chain for the MOVING project. The specificities of the researched area in the context of agricultural production include the small number of farms with a relatively large farmed area, the lack of small landowners due to historical development, the historical interdependence with the original state-owned farms and the necessary cooperation with the Šumava National Park. In our research on beef production in Šumava mountains, we found that only a minority of farmers have so far managed to develop the beef production value chain from cattle breeding, through slaughtering and processing to direct sales to customers. However, within this practice (compared to the sale of stocker cattle), the greatest value added remains in the locality. One of the outputs of the project is therefore to identify barriers to the spread of this production method among other farmers in the locality. At the same time, by using examples of good practice, the project can help to promote integrated beef production within the locality among other actors. Another output of the project is to assess the different interests of the key actors using the Šumava mountain areas (farmers, tourists and the Šumava National Park) and to try to find a balance between these interests with regard to the further development of the Šumava mountain areas.

MOVING Reference Region Šumava - Cesky Les
Country Czechia
Authors Lukáš Zagata, Jakub Husák (CZU)
More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/sumava-cesky-les-czechia/

Native language

Produkce hovězího masa na Šumavě

Extenzivní chov skotu a produkce hovězího masa je tradičním a hojně rozšířeným způsobem obhospodařování půdy v horských oblastech Šumavy. Stejně jako jiné oblasti, tak i Šumava je zasažena globálními změnami klimatu, které ovlivňují i tamní zemědělskou produkci. To jsou hlavní důvody pro výběr hodnotového řetězce produkce hovězího masa pro řešení v rámci projektu MOVING. Mezi specifika zkoumané lokality v kontextu zemědělské produkce patří především malý počet podniků s relativně velkou obhospodařovanou výměrou, v důsledku historického vývoje chybějící drobní vlastníci půdy, historická provázanost s původními státními statky a nezbytná spolupráce s Národním parkem Šumava. V rámci zkoumání produkce hovězího masa na Šumavě jsme odhalili, že pouze menší část zemědělců zatím dokázala rozvinout celý hodnotový řetězec od chovu skotu, přes jeho porážku a zpracování, až po přímý prodej zákazníkům. Přitom v rámci této praxe (oproti prodeji zástavového skotu) zůstává největší přidaná hodnota v lokalitě. Jedním z dílčích výstupů projektu je tedy odhalení bariér bránících rozšíření tohoto způsobu produkce i mezi dalšími zemědělci v lokalitě. Zároveň může projekt s využitím příkladů dobré praxe napomoci komplexní produkci hovězího masa v lokalitě i u dalších aktérů. Dalším výstupem projektu je zhodnocení rozličných zájmů klíčových aktérů využívajících horské oblasti Šumavy (zemědělci, turisté a Národní park Šumava) a snaha o nalezení rovnováhy těchto zájmů s ohledem na další rozvoj horských oblastí Šumavy.

4. The conditions for maintaining the Corsican chestnut grove and the production of Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) flour in the face of its new uses and bioclimatic issues

The "farina castagnina" Value Chain (VC), in PDO since 2010, is the result of the revival of an activity at the heart of the old food system of Corsica. The chestnut grove covers an area of 35,000 ha and has around fifty varieties. The valorization of flour gave an institutional and commercial existence to chestnut farming. In 2019, there were 69 castaneiculturists, 3 millers and 55 processors on the island (combining production, dryer, oven and mill). Before the arrival of the cynips disease, the production of PDO flour varied from 110 to 200 tonnes for a declared area of 700 ha. The VC takes advantage of a demanding and remunerative market that retains the features of a mountain domestic activity (direct sales, interpersonal networks, fairs, local stores, e-commerce).

In addition, the chestnut grove is a resource for 4 other PDOs (Lonzu, Prisuttu, Coppa, Mele di Corsica) and for other productive and non-productive activities (timber, education, tourism, development, etc.). However, the strong mobilization of the ecosystem is not enough to deal with old and new vulnerabilities (abandonment, aging trees, diseases and climate change). The challenges are to maintain or even increase the orchards in the project area (renovation, planting), to consolidate the production of PDO flour, to identify the strategies and conditions (technical and organizational) for the coexistence of the different uses of trees and orchards. It is expected that a device combining the production of knowledge and the establishment of management rules will be set up in the Mountain Reference Landscape, bringing together VC operators, local elected officials, associations and institutions involved (Regional Natural Park of Corsica, regions and consulars).

MOVING Reference Region
Corsica
Country France
Authors Jean Michel Sorba (INRAE - UMR Selmets-LRDE)
More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/corsica-france/

Native language

Les conditions de maintien de la châtaigneraie corse et de la production de farine AOP face à ses nouveaux usages et aux enjeux bioclimatiques.

La Chaîne de Valeur (CV) «AOP farina castagnina» constitue le cœur de l'ancien système alimentaire de la Corse. La châtaigneraie couvre 35 000 ha pour une cinquantaine de variétés. La mobilisation des communautés villageoises et la certification de la farine ont donné une existence institutionnelle, professionnelle et marchande à la castanéiculture (69 castanéiculteurs, dont 55 transformateurs, et 3 meuniers). La CV tire parti d'un marché demandeur et rémunérateur caractéristique d'une activité domestique montagnarde (vente directe, réseaux interpersonnels, foires, magasins locaux). Par ailleurs, la châtaigneraie constitue un milieu-ressource pour 4 autres AOP (Lonzu, Prisuttu, Coppa, Mele di Corsica) et pour d'autres activités productives et de services (bois, éducation, tourisme, aménagement...). Avant l'arrivée du cynips en 2011, la production de farines AOP variait de 110 à 200 tonnes pour une surface déclarée de 700 ha. La forte utilisation de l'écosystème accroît ses vulnérabilités (abandon, vieillissement des arbres, maladies et changement climatique). Le maintien de la châtaigneraie en Corse suppose de concevoir une nouvelle approche comprenant une stratégie de renouvellement des vergers anciens (rénovation, régénération, plantation), la consolidation de la production de farine en AOP et la conception d'une organisation rendant possible la coexistence des différents usages des arbres et des vergers. Il est attendu du projet Moving, la mise en place d'un dispositif dans le territoire de montagne de référence (Mountain Reference Landscape) combinant la production de connaissances et la mise en place de règles de gestion associant les producteurs, les élus, les associations et les institutions parties prenantes.

5. Pastoralism, a sustainable practice for the production of quality sheep meat

The sheep meat value chain is fully integrated in the Drôme mountainous context because of its extensive model. The value and the quality of the final product are expressed by the healthy environment in which the animal grew up, the resources it was fed with and the easy accessibility of the slaughtering and processing sites. Almost all lambs are raised on grass: the animals are left free or semi-free range in their natural environment for most of the year. The marketing of the lambs is mainly done by direct sale or in local food network, and a small part via a cooperative. The lambs are sold by carcass or half carcass, an approach that allows to value the whole animal. The pastoral activity of the sector produces a large number of positive externalities through the management of natural areas and the regulation of the environment. However, the sector is facing many problems: drought and rising temperatures are impacting the quality of grassland resources and making it difficult to supply water to the mountain pastures. The phenomenon of predation is today the main concern for breeders. Finally, land use conflicts lead to new sources of tension between local actors. Different strategies have been identified to ensure the viability of the sector: support and accompany pastoral groups (PG); develop undergrowth grazing; raise awareness of the predation context and the fortify cohabitation with livestock activities in the mountains; promote synergies with the tourism sector.

MOVING Reference Region
Drome Valley
Country France
Authors Marco Trentin (CCVD)
More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/drome-valley-france/

Native language

Le pastoralisme, une pratique durable pour la production de viande ovine de qualité

La filière viande ovine s'inscrit pleinement dans le contexte montagnard drômois en raison de son modèle extensif. La valeur et la qualité du produit final s'expriment par l'environnement sain dans lequel l'animal a grandi, les ressources dont il a été nourri et la facilité d'accès au site d'abattage et de transformation. La majorité des agneaux sont élevés à l'herbe: les animaux sont laissés en liberté ou en semi-liberté dans leur environnement naturel pendant la majeure partie de l'année. La commercialisation des agneaux se fait principalement par vente directe ou en circuit court, et une petite partie via une coopérative. L'activité pastorale du secteur produit un grand nombre d'externalités positives par la gestion des espaces naturels et la régulation des milieux. Cependant, le secteur est confronté à de nombreux problèmes: la sécheresse et la hausse des températures ont un impact sur la qualité des ressources herbagères et rendent difficile l'approvisionnement en eau dans les alpages. Le contexte de prédation effrénée inquiète les éleveurs. Enfin, les conflits d'usage entraînent de nouvelles sources de tension entre les acteurs locaux. Différentes stratégies ont été identifiées pour assurer la viabilité de la filière : soutenir et accompagner les groupements pastoraux (GP) ; développer le pâturage en sous-bois ; sensibiliser au contexte de prédation et à la cohabitation avec les activités d'élevage en montagne ; favoriser les synergies avec le secteur touristique.

6. The carob flour value chain and its sustainability in Rethymno

Carob cultivation contributed to the sustainability of the rural areas of Rethymno for centuries. The farming practices used for its cultivation have been under threat from the subsidized olive monoculture, the low price of carob and the abandonment of village life in the past decades. More recently, there are signs of carob's revival because of its nutritional value and local carob flour's use in the production of innovative, yet culturally resonant products that are gaining market space. The local carob pod production and processing businesses face challenges in meeting the market demands, offering unique quality and ensuring the trust of consumers in the face of foreign competition. Obstacles include systematic carob cultivation and processing due to lack of knowledge and support for the farmers and mills, the complicated national and regional regulatory context and the fluctuations of carob's price in international markets. Carob's higher prices in recent years and its resilience to climatic change may provide renewed opportunities for carob cultivation and its expansion in the higher altitudes of Rethymno. The development of more cohesive relationships in the carob community will benefit farmers and agricultural businesses by co-creating knowledge and wider synergies among the stakeholders, while maintaining commitment to environmental, economic and cultural sustainability of the mountainous and semi-mountainous villages and landscapes. Communal deliberation may also provoke a review of Crete's rural development strategic plans.

MOVING Reference Region
Crete
Country Greece
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More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/crete-greece/

Native language

Βιωσιμότητα της αλυσίδας αξίας του χαρουπάλευρου στο Ρέθυμνο

Η καλλιέργεια της χαρουπιάς συνέβαλλε στη βιωσιμότητα των αγροτικών περιοχών του Ρεθύμνου για αιώνες. Οι γεωργικές πρακτικές που χρησιμοποιούνται για την καλλιέργειά του απειλούνται από την επιδοτούμενη μονοκαλλιέργεια ελιάς, τη χαμηλή τιμή του χαρουπιού και την εγκατάλειψη των χωριών τις τελευταίες δεκαετίες. Πρόσφατα υπάρχουν ενδείξεις αναβίωσης του χαρουπιού λόγω της διατροφικής του αξίας και της χρήσης του τοπικού χαρουπάλευρου στην παραγωγή καινοτόμων, αλλά συνάμα παραδοσιακών προϊόντων που κερδίζουν χώρο στην αγορά. Οι τοπικές επιχειρήσεις παραγωγής και επεξεργασίας χαρουπιών αντιμετωπίζουν προκλήσεις για την κάλυψη των απαιτήσεων της αγοράς, την προσφορά μοναδικής ποιότητας και τη διασφάλιση της εμπιστοσύνης των καταναλωτών απέναντι στον ξένο ανταγωνισμό. Τα εμπόδια αφορούν στη συστηματική καλλιέργεια και επεξεργασία του χαρουπιού λόγω έλλειψης γνώσεων, στην υποστήριξη για τους αγρότες και τους μύλους, στο περίπλοκο εθνικό και περιφερειακό κανονιστικό πλαίσιο και στις διακυμάνσεις της τιμής του χαρουπιού στις διεθνείς αγορές. Οι υψηλότερες τιμές των τελευταίων ετών και η ανθεκτικότητα του χαρουπιού στην κλιματική αλλαγή μπορεί να δώσει μια νέα ευκαιρία στην καλλιέργεια της χαρουπιάς και την επέκτασή της και σε μεγαλύτερα υψόμετρα. Η ανάπτυξη μιας συνεκτικής κοινότητας ατόμων που ασχολούνται με το χαρούπι θα ωφελήσει τους αγρότες συνδημιουργώντας γνώσεις και συνέργειες ανάμεσα στους εμπλεκόμενους, διατηρώντας παράλληλα τη δέσμευση για περιβαλλοντική, οικονομική και πολιτιστική βιωσιμότητα των ορεινών και ημιορεινών χωριών και τοπίων. Ο κοινοτικός διάλογος μπορεί να προκαλέσει αναθεώρηση των στρατηγικών σχεδίων αγροτικής ανάπτυξης της Κρήτης.

7. Knowledge economy for sustainable livelihoods - Cold Mountain Shelter value chain analysis in Transdanubian mountain reference landscape

Cold Mountain Shelter is a growing community of young, educated environmentally conscious lifestyle migrants. They live mostly off grid, with sustainable solutions for energy and water management, producing food through permaculture, forest agriculture, contour farming, extensive animal husbandry, etc. Nevertheless, their main ‘products’ are in knowledge economy as they are developing a complex, organic, lived-knowledge-base on sustainable livelihoods. They organise courses, events, exhibitions in permaculture, orcharding, sustainable water/energy management, construction and community building. Through a nation-wide association of lifestyle migrants (All-goes-together

Association) they participate in creating an online platform to share environmental- and community friendly technology (both innovative and traditional) organising a yearly festival and helping to develop local and regional nodes of environmentally conscious communities. Their activities are relevant for land use, saving and creating environmental and community values, and it is an excellent example of how a conscious and powerful community can create and spread knowledge about resilience and sustainability. They innovate, combine traditional knowledge with technology, creating completely new frameworks and patterns, showing an alternative, and real life solutions for some of the most important problems of our times, representing an important socio-economic trend, spreading fast in developed countries.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Transdanubian Mountains</p>
<p>Country</p> <p>Hungary</p>
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<p>More info</p> <p>https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/transdanubian-mountains-hungary/</p>

Native language

A fenntartható életvitel tudásgazdasága – A Dunántúli-középhegységben található Hideghegyi Menedék értéklánc elemzése

A Hideghegyi Menedék fiatal, művelt, környezettudatos életmódot folytató életmódvándorok közössége. Off-grid életet élnek, fenntartható energia- és vízgazdálkodási megoldásokkal, élelmük nagy részét környezetkímélő gazdálkodási módokon keresztül (permakultúra, erdőkert, gyümölcsészet, szintvonalas gazdálkodás, extenzív állattartás stb) maguk termelik. Ugyanakkor fő termékeiket a tudásalapú gazdaságban találjuk, a fenntartható étellel kapcsolatos, komplex, organikus, megélt tudásbázis felépítésén dolgoznak. Tanfolyamokat, rendezvényeket, táborokat szerveznek a permakultúra, a gyümölcsészet, a fenntartható víz- és energiagazdálkodás, az építőipar és a közösségépítés területén. Országos szervezetükön keresztül (Mindenegyüttmegye Egyesület) részt vesznek egy online platform létrehozásában a környezet- és közösségbarát technológiák (innovatív és hagyományos) megosztására, a Gyüttment fesztivált szervezik és segítenek a környezettudatos közösségek helyi és regionális csomópontjainak kialakításában. Tevékenységük releváns a fenntartható földhasználat, a környezeti és közösségi értékek megőrzésének szempontjából, és kiváló példa arra, hogy egy tudatos és erős közösség hogyan hozhat létre és terjeszthet megélt tudást a fenntartható étellel kapcsolatban. Újítanak, a hagyományos tudást ötvözik modern technológiával, új mintákat hoznak létre, alternatívát és valós életszerű megoldásokat mutatva korunk égető problémáira, a fejlett országokban gyorsan terjedő társadalmi-gazdasági trendeket képviselve.

8. Milk matters in Alto Molise

Dairy production is historically rooted in Alto Molise. It connects local economic actors, such as breeders, shepherds, cheesemakers, suppliers of goods and services, local institutions that give access to common pastures, and the tourism sector due to winter and rural tourism. Cheesemaking is an artisanal craft that is often passed down through generations. The cheesemakers rely mostly on raw milk from local breeders. The typical products are mainly the Caciocavallo and the straciatina. The marketing strategy connects the dairy productions with Alto Molise's traditions and local natural resources. The distribution is usually towards the local dairy farm shop, specialty shops, large-scale distribution and e-commerce. Consumption is mostly local for fresh cheese products; aged products are sold at national and international level. The main cheesemakers promote innovation by creating new products, innovative marketing strategies, implementing new packaging to increase products' shelf life and investing in digital technology (i.e software for sales and warehouse management). The findings indicate that there is a level of activity and employment that allows a part of the population to remain in the area (despite the depopulation trend), as well as a revival of cultural tradition and heritage, and a valorisation of natural resource conservation. Interventions in raw material quality linked to milk price, based on pasture resources, should be supported. The assemblage of the dairy value chain with tourism and meat production, in sustainable ways, can boost product awareness and income diversification, but investments in infrastructure, as well as reinforcing joint milk/meat farming methods are needed.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Central Apennines</p>
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Native language

L'importanza del latte in Alto Molise

La produzione lattiero-casearia è storicamente radicata in Alto Molise. Mette in relazione attori economici locali, come allevatori, pastori, casari, istituzioni locali. La produzione di formaggio è un'attività artigianale che viene tramandata di generazione in generazione. I casari si affidano soprattutto al latte crudo degli allevatori locali. I prodotti tipici sono in particolare il caciocavallo e la stracciata. La strategia di marketing mette in relazione le produzioni casearie con le tradizioni dell'Alto Molise e le risorse naturali locali. La distribuzione avviene generalmente verso il normal trade e le gastronomie, ma anche attraverso la GDO e l'e-commerce. Il consumo è prevalentemente locale per i prodotti caseari freschi; i prodotti stagionati sono venduti a livello nazionale e internazionale. I principali caseifici promuovono l'innovazione attraverso la creazione di nuovi prodotti, il marketing relazionale, il packaging e le tecnologie digitali. I risultati indicano che esiste un livello di attività e di occupazione che consente a una parte della popolazione di rimanere nell'area (nonostante la tendenza allo spopolamento), nonché un recupero e valorizzazione della tradizione e del patrimonio culturale. Andrebbero incoraggiati interventi sulla qualità della materia prima connessi al prezzo del latte in base al ricorso alle risorse locali (pascoli). L'abbinamento con il turismo e la produzione di carne, in modo sostenibile, può aumentare la consapevolezza del prodotto e la diversificazione del reddito, ma sono necessari investimenti in infrastrutture e il rafforzamento dei metodi di allevamento congiunto di latte e carne.

9. Mountain wine and territory in Trentino

Viticulture in Trentino has a long tradition and in the last decade both the area involved and the notoriety of the wines (especially Trento Protected Denomination of Origin-DOC), sparkling wine obtained with the champenois method, but also several autochthonous wines, both white and red, vinified with the normal method) kept increasing. Viticultural production is essentially based on small producers, often with areas of about 1ha, who supply the grapes to cooperative wineries or private groups. The amount of grape directly processed by smallholders is increasing but still a limited share. In all cases, the wines produced are placed in a medium-high range of the market. As a result of climate change, viticulture has begun to move to the highest slopes of the Trentino valleys, reaching 900 m, where some pioneers have begun to cultivate resistant vines (PIWI), often adapting the winemaking method. They were followed by the more structured farms in the lower valley which identified the most suitable areas for the cultivation of the standard varieties. The work carried out by larger companies can also benefit small winemakers, who can profit from the infrastructures and knowledge developed by the former. Cultivation in the mountains poses some problems, such as water availability, the management of soil fertility, especially in terms of organic matter, the management of pests and diseases with different cycles from the valley floor. Unlike other mountain areas, Trentino agriculture manages to maintain a relatively good profitability even for smallholders, especially thanks to viticulture, the connection with tourism and transversal collaboration.

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Eastern Alps
Country Italy
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Native language

Vino di montagna e territorio in Trentino

La viticoltura in Trentino ha una lunga tradizione e nell'ultimo decennio continua ad aumentare sia la superficie coinvolta che la notorietà dei vini (soprattutto la Denominazione di Origine Controllata- DOC- Trento), ottenuto con metodo classico, ma anche diversi autoctoni, sia bianchi che rossi, vinificati con metodo normale). La produzione viticola si basa essenzialmente su piccoli produttori, spesso con superfici di circa 1ha, che conferiscono a cantine cooperative o gruppi privati, in aumento ma ancora minoritaria la quantità di uva vinificata dagli stessi viticoltori. I vini prodotti si collocano su una fascia medio-alta di mercato. Sulla spinta del cambiamento climatico la viticoltura ha iniziato a spostarsi sulle pendici più alte delle valli Trentine, arrivando a 900m, dove alcuni pionieri hanno iniziato a coltivare vitigni resistenti (PIWI), adattando anche il metodo di vinificazione. Ad essi sono seguite le aziende più strutturate della bassa vallata che hanno identificato gli areali più adeguati alla coltivazione anche delle varietà standard. Il lavoro svolto dalle aziende più grandi ritorna a beneficio anche dei piccoli viticoltori, che possono fruire delle infrastrutture e delle conoscenze sviluppate dai primi. La coltivazione in montagna pone delle problematiche, come la disponibilità idrica, la gestione della fertilità dei suoli, soprattutto in termini di sostanza organica, la gestione di patogeni e parassiti con cicli diversi dal fondovalle. Diversamente da altre aree di montagna, l'agricoltura Trentina riesce a mantenere una relativamente buona redditività anche per le aziende di piccole dimensioni, soprattutto grazie alla viticoltura, al collegamento con il turismo ed alla collaborazione trasversale.

10. The Chestnut flour value chain and its sustainability in Alta Versilia (Tuscany)

Italy is among the world's leading producers and exporters of chestnuts. Chestnut groves represent 7.53% of the national forest and covers about 780,000 ha. After several decades of total abandonment - in Tuscany alone, there are estimated to be around 17,000 ha. of abandoned chestnut trees - recently a renewed interest in this cultivation has emerged. Chestnut is indeed an important multipurpose tree species for its resistant wood and its edible fruits. Its flour has been the main source of food for entire populations, it has deep roots in the Tuscany rural tradition and history. Specifically in Alta Versilia, the production of chestnut flour still follows traditional methods: the harvesting and selection of the fruit are done manually, and the slow drying process takes place in small buildings with stone slab roofs, called metato. Traditionally, each family had its own metato; today, the same building is used collectively. The community interactions, the high quality of the flour with high demand compared to the scarce supply and the relatively good price (up to 15 €/kg) make the value chain of chestnut flour in Alta Versilia an opportunity for the valorisation of the unique set of natural, social, and cultural capitals that characterise the territory. Therefore, the challenge is to increase the production of flour, starting with reducing the abandonment of the chestnut tree and managing the process in structured way, without losing the traditional taste. There are some local business associations that are trying to lead this change, introducing some innovations in the marketing strategies (e.g., new packaging, use of social networks) and a more organised system.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Northern Apennines</p>
<p>Country</p> <p>Italy</p>
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Native language

La catena del valore della farina di castagne e la sua sostenibilità in Alta Versilia (Toscana)

L'Italia è tra i principali produttori ed esportatori di castagne. I castagneti rappresentano il 7,53% del patrimonio forestale nazionale e coprono circa 780.000 ettari. Dopo alcuni decenni di totale abbandono - solo in Toscana si stimano 17.000 ettari di castagneti abbandonati - di recente è emerso un rinnovato interesse per questa coltivazione. Il castagno è infatti un'importante specie arborea polivalente per il suo legno resistente e i suoi frutti. La sua farina che ha rappresentato la principale fonte di alimentazione per intere popolazioni, ha profonde radici nella tradizione e nella storia rurale toscana. Nello specifico in Alta Versilia, la produzione di farina di castagne segue ancora metodi tradizionali: la raccolta e la selezione dei frutti avvengono a mano e il lento processo di essiccazione avviene in piccoli edifici con tetti in lastre di pietra, chiamati "metato". Tradizionalmente, ogni famiglia possedeva il proprio metato; oggi, lo stesso è utilizzato collettivamente. Le interazioni comunitarie, l'alta qualità della farina con una domanda elevata rispetto all'offerta e un prezzo relativamente buono, rendono la catena del valore della farina di castagne in Alta Versilia un'opportunità per la valorizzazione dell'insieme unico di capitali naturali, sociali e culturali che caratterizzano il territorio. La sfida è quella di aumentare la produzione di farina, partendo dalla riduzione dell'abbandono del castagno e dalla gestione del processo di produzione in modo strutturato, senza perdere il gusto. Ci sono alcune associazioni imprenditoriali locali che stanno cercando di guidare questo cambiamento e hanno introdotte alcune innovazioni nelle strategie di marketing e un sistema più organizzato.

11. Rural tourism value chain analysis in Maleshevski mountains reference landscape

The Maleshevski Mountains cover the municipalities of Berovo and Pehchevo. They are known for their outstanding natural and cultural value, and rural tourism here has a long tradition. Main key practices in Maleshevski mountains region are: Development of rural tourism through target groups – mountainous social activities; Specific regional traditional and agricultural food products offers – local businesses; Employment of young people especially in the tourism sector; Including the environmental aspect among the social and economic. Key economic values/outcomes are: Increasing the workforce in the tourism sector, increasing the number of ecotourism start-ups, integrating regional companies into the tourism value chain, development of green economy. Key socio-cultural values/outcomes are: Improving social life among young generations, involvement of women in the activities, increasing mountain bike matches, restaurants visits, hiking tours, cultural landmarks visits, traditional caterings and specialties, reduced rate of unemployment and migration in the region. Key environmental values/outcomes are: Experience- sharing for agro-forestry eco values, reducing CO₂ emissions/pollution in the region, reduced resource consumption, reduced amount of waste, supporting eco-restaurants, use of regional agroforestry species to make other plant based products, informations about forest management activities, floral and faunal diversity of the region and wildfires prevention.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Maleshevski mountains</p>
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Native language

Анализа на синџирот на вредности во Малешевскиот референтен пејзаж

Малешевските планини ги опфаќаат општините Берово и Пехчево. Тие се познати по нивната извонредна природна и културна вредност, а руралниот туризам овде има долга традиција. Главни клучни практики во регионот на Малешевските планини се: Развој на рурален туризам преку целни групи – планински социјални активности; Специфични регионални понуди за традиционални и земјоделски прехранбени производи – локални бизниси; Вработување на млади особено во секторот туризам; Вклучувајќи го еколошкиот аспект меѓу социјалниот и економскиот. Клучни економски вредности/резултати се: Зголемување на работната сила во секторот туризам, зголемување на бројот на стартапи за екотуризам, интегрирање на регионалните компании во синџирот на вредност на туризмот, развој на зелена економија. Клучните социо-културни вредности/резултати се: Подобрвање на социјалниот живот кај младите генерации, вклученост на жените во активностите, зголемување на натпреварите за планински велосипедизам, посети на ресторани, планинарски тури, посети на културни знаменитости, традиционални угостителски и специјалитети, намалена стапка на невработеност и миграција во регионот. Клучни еколошки вредности/резултати се: споделување искуства за агрошумарските еколошки вредности, намалување на емисиите/загадувањето со CO₂ во регионот, намалена потрошувачка на ресурси, намалено количество отпад, поддршка на еко-ресторани, употреба на регионални агрошумски видови за производство на други растенија производи базирани, Информации за активностите за управување со шумите, разновидноста на флората и фауната во регионот и превенција од шумски пожари.

12. The mountain landscape and PDO products - the case of Serra da Estrela cheese

Serra da Estrela cheese is one of the most recognized cheeses in Portugal. It follows strict specifications in order to earn its Protected Designation of Origin (PDO), that recognises the strong link between products and the place in which they are made. Not only the milk and cheese have to be produced within the designated area, the cheese is made exclusively with milk from native sheep breeds – Bordaleira Serra da Estrela and Churra Mondegueira – and submitted to a sensorial test before being certified.

Considering these production requirements, but also its value in the local history and culture, the connection between the cheese and Serra da Estrela is undeniable. The introduction of innovations such as improved pastures and fences, and advances in livelihoods, have changed how the value chain interacts with the region at its core – the landscape. Fewer sheep and shepherds and the abandonment of transhumance mean the use of permanent and altitude pasture is disappearing in favour of foothill grazing. The mountain landscape is degrading (or at the very least, changing) while the value chain of the cheese thrives.

EU's geographic indications alone are not enough to have a clear territorial connection between product and landscape. If maintaining the landscape and its associated services and benefits is a goal, it needs to exist incentives to use it. Shepherds ought to be financially compensated for using altitude pastures as a service they are paying, and their life quality needs to be secured. This could be through municipal cooperation in organizing shepherds so that they don't have to spend a whole season in altitude, providing network coverage and shelters.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Cordilheira central</p>
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Native language

Produtos DOP e paisagem de montanha - o caso do queijo Serra da Estrela

O queijo Serra da Estrela é um dos queijos mais reconhecidos em Portugal. Segue um caderno de especificações rígido para obter a sua Denominação de Origem Protegida (DOP), que reconhece a forte ligação entre os produtos e o local em que são produzidos. Não só o leite e o queijo têm de ser produzidos dentro da área designada, o queijo é fabricado exclusivamente com leite de raças ovinas autóctones - Bordaleira Serra da Estrela e Churra Mondegueira - e submetido a um teste sensorial antes de ser certificado.

Tendo em conta estes requisitos de produção, mas também o seu valor na história e cultura locais, a ligação entre o queijo e a Serra da Estrela é inegável. No entanto, a introdução de inovações como a melhoria das pastagens, e os avanços no que é considerado qualidade de vida, alteraram a forma como a cadeia de valor interage com a paisagem. Redução no número de ovelhas e pastores e o abandono da transumância significam que a utilização de pastagens permanentes e de altitude está a desaparecer a favor do pastoreio no sopé da montanha. A paisagem da montanha está a degradar-se (ou, no mínimo, a mudar) enquanto a cadeia de valor do queijo continua.

As indicações geográficas da UE, por si só, não são suficientes para ter uma clara ligação territorial entre produto e paisagem. Se a manutenção da paisagem e dos seus serviços e benefícios associados é um objectivo, é necessário que existam incentivos para a sua utilização. Os pastores devem ser compensados financeiramente pela utilização de pastagens de altitude como um serviço que estão a pagar, e a sua qualidade de vida precisa de ser assegurada. Isto poderia ser através da cooperação municipal na organização dos pastores, para que não tenham de passar uma estação inteira em altitude, fornecendo cobertura de rede e abrigos.

13. The Eastern Douro wines

Douro was the first Protected Denomination of Origin, PDO, wine area to be defined and ruled at world level. In the Douro eastern sub-region, the Alto Douro Vinhateiro, viticulture faces more stringent constraints linked to steep slopes and specific climatic conditions. Viticulture is practiced on terraces built with schistous stones, hosting only 1 or 2 lines of grapevine each, fact that limits mechanization and increases labour costs. The beauty of the landscape, mainly built by viticulture, led UNESCO to declare the Alto Douro Vinhateiro a World Heritage Cultural and Evolving Landscape. In the area of Vila Nova da Foz Côa, South Eastern part of Alto Douro, the landscape is even more complex and intertwined with almonds, olive groves and large part of shrubs and woods. In this area, viticulture is now regaining importance after decades of decline. The typical wines produced here are Barca velha and other white wines. They are processed by few small-holders, a cooperative cellar and by an increasing number of large companies, based in the Western and more developed area of the PDO region. Foz Côa valley was also acknowledged by Unesco as World Heritage as "the most important open air Palaeolithic rock art site", creating quite a unique situation of 2 UNESCO acknowledgments in the same area. This increases the touristic potential of the area, whose attractiveness is based on the viticulture landscape, the Paleolithic engravings and the possibility to practice several leisure activities. The main hindering factor for the development of the rural area is depopulation, due to lack of qualified job opportunities, infrastructures and services. The recent investments of large wine companies do not significantly increase the added value that stays in the area.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Maciço Noroeste</p>
<p>Country</p> <p>Portugal</p>
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Native language

Os vinhos do Douro do este

A Região Demarcada Douro foi a primeira a ser definida e regulamentada a nível mundial. No Alto Douro Vinhateiro, a parte oriental do vale do Douro, a viticultura enfrenta serios constrangimentos ligados a declives acentuados e condições climáticas específicas. A viticultura é praticada em socalcos construídos com pedras xistosas, albergando apenas 1 ou 2 linhas de vinha cada, facto que limita a mecanização e aumenta os custos de mão-de-obra. A beleza da paisagem, construída pela viticultura, levou a UNESCO a declarar o Alto Douro Vinhateiro Património da Humanidade, Paisagem Cultural e Evolutiva. Na zona de Vila Nova da Foz Côa, no sudeste do Alto Douro, a paisagem é ainda mais complexa e entrelaçada com amendoeiras, olivais e muita parte de bosques. Nesta área, a viticultura está agora a recuperar importância após décadas de declínio. Os vinhos típicos são o Barca Velha e outros vinhos brancos, processados por poucos pequenos proprietários, uma adega cooperativa e por um número crescente de grandes empresas, sediadas na área ocidental da região demarcada. O vale de Foz Côa foi também reconhecido pela Unesco como Património Mundial como “o mais importante sítio de arte rupestre paleolítica a céu aberto”, criando uma situação bastante especial de 2 reconhecimentos da UNESCO na mesma área. Isso aumenta o potencial turístico da região, cujos atrativos se baseiam na paisagem vitícola, nas gravuras paleolíticas e na possibilidade de praticar diversas atividades de lazer. O principal entrave ao desenvolvimento do meio rural é o despovoamento, devido à falta de oportunidades de trabalho qualificado, infra-estruturas e serviços. Os recentes investimentos de grandes empresas vitivinícolas não aumentam o valor acrescentado que se mantém na região.

14. Certified Ecotourism value chain analysis in the Zărnești – Piatra Craiului 'eco-destination'

The Piatra Craiului National Park and surrounding area are part of the Southern Romanian Carpathians. The area has a unique mountain landscape dominated by a 25 km long limestone ridge, mixed forest and a patchwork of small farms that is highly appreciated nationally and internationally. However, it is also a fragile landscape and vulnerable ecosystem that is under growing pressure. The traditional rural identity is increasingly eroded by an urbanised form of over-development which is tending to discourage more discerning visitors. A major challenge now is how to promote and manage the growth of tourism in a way that continues to provide economic benefits for local people without risk of negative impact upon the valuable natural assets of the region.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Southern Romanian Carpathian mountains</p>
<p>Country</p> <p>Romania</p>
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One solution is the development and adoption of alternative forms of tourism that can contribute to the sustainable development of local communities, while protecting the local biodiversity, landscape, and cultural heritage. Ecotourism is a form of tourism where the main motivation of the tourist is to observe and enjoy both nature (landscape and biodiversity) and the traditional local customs, including food. Such an approach is well-suited to the sustainable development of local rural economies and the Zărnești – Piatra Craiului region is one of ten 'eco-destinations' certified and promoted by Association of Ecotourism in Romania (www.eco-romania.ro/en/eco-destinations/zarnesti-piatra-craiului/).

The MOVING project (www.moving-h2020.eu/) is studying the main characteristics of the ecotourism value chain in the region and will make recommendations for enhancing its contribution to sustainable local development.

Native language

Analiza lanțului de valoare ecoturism certificat în „eco-destinația” Zărnești – Piatra Craiului

Parcul Național Piatra Craiului și zona înconjurătoare fac parte din Carpații Meridionali. Zona are un peisaj montan unic dominat de o creastă calcaroasă de 25 de km, păduri mixte și un mix de mici gospodării foarte apreciat atât la nivel național, cât și internațional. Însă parcul reprezintă și un peisaj fragil și un ecosistem din ce în ce mai vulnerabil. Identitatea rurală tradițională a regiunii a fost afectată de-a lungul timpului de o dezvoltare de tip urban care descurajează turismul responsabil. O mare provocare este identificarea unor modalități de promovare și coordonare a creșterii turismului într-un mod care să continue să ofere beneficii economice pentru populația locală, fără a exista riscul unui impact negativ asupra resurselor naturale importante ale regiunii.

O soluție este dezvoltarea și adoptarea de forme alternative de turism care pot contribui la dezvoltarea sustenabilă a comunităților locale, protejând în același timp biodiversitatea, peisajul și patrimoniul cultural. Ecoturismul este o formă de turism în care principala dorință a turistului este de a observa și de a se bucura de natură (peisaj și biodiversitate), și de tradițiile și gastronomia locale. O astfel de abordare este potrivită pentru dezvoltarea sustenabilă a economiei locale din Parcul Național Piatra Craiului, iar regiunea Zărnești – Piatra Craiului este una dintre cele 10 „eco-destinații” promovate de Asociația de Ecoturism din România (<https://www.eco-romania.ro/eco-destinatii/zarnesti-piatra-craiului/>).

Proiectul MOVING (www.moving-h2020.eu/) va evidenția principalele caracteristici ale lanțului de valoare, și va face propuneri pentru îmbunătățirea contribuției acestuia la dezvoltarea locală durabilă.

15. Transitioning towards a short Sjenica lamb value chain managed by producers

Sjenica sheep is an autochthonous breed of the Pester plateau, adapted to its harsh climate. Plateau is in the Western Serbia Dinaric Mountains (Zlatar – Pester group), at the border with Montenegro and BIH.

Sjenica sheep is characterised by high quality meat, good milk yields and fine wool. Sjenica Lamb Meat and the two interconnected products – Sjenica Cheese and Stelja (preserved meat) are registered as Protected Designation of Origin (PDO).

The Sjenica Lamb VC with its nomadic, extensive breeding is deeply rooted in the tradition of the region (first written records are from 16th century). Sheeps are grazed on natural pastures, using traditional seasonal “katun”, for at least 6 months (May-October). Parts of the Pester plateau used for grazing belong to the Ramsar and other natural protected areas, rich in medical and aromatic plants. During winter, sheeps are fed with hay and small percentage of mostly locally grown grains (up to 5%).

The Sjenica lamb VC analysis showed that high reputation of the three interconnected VCs is not yet valorised. Weak linkages between producers and absence of functional groups create space for intermediaries, who take the added value outside of the region. Shortening the VCs would exclude them, being the first step for bringing back the added value to the region.

Different community initiatives and projects linking rural development and adding value to the products, would contribute to VC improvement. Innovations (innovative usage of wool, breeding centres, IT solutions, etc.), specialized producer group creation, specifically targeted and tailor made marketing strategies, could bring new strength and effectiveness to the current VCs. The focus should be on supporting young people who still remain in the area.

MOVING Reference Region Dinaric Mountains
Country Serbia
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More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/dinaric-mountains-serbia/

Native language

Prelazak na kratak lanac proizvodnje Sjeničke jagnjetine kojim upravljaju proizvođači

Sjenička ovca je autohtona rasa Pešterske visoravni, prilagođena njenoj oštroj klimi. Visoravan se nalazi na Dinarskim planinama zapadne Srbije (grupa Zlatar – Pešter), na granici sa Crnom Gorom i BiH. Sjeničku ovcu odlikuje kvalitetno meso, dobra mlečnost i fina vuna. Sjeničko jagnjeće meso i dva povezana proizvoda – Sjenički sir i Stelja suvomesnati proizvod) registrovani su kao Zaštićeno ime porekla (PDO). VC Sjeničke jagnjetine sa svojim nomadskim, ekstenzivnim uzgojem duboko je ukorenjen u tradiciji ovog kraja (prvi pisani zapisi su iz 16. veka). Ovce se napasaju na prirodnim pašnjacima, koristeći tradicionalni sezonski katun, najmanje 6 meseci (maj-oktobar). Delovi Pešterske visoravni koji se koriste za ispašu pripadaju Ramsarskom i drugim prirodnim zaštićenim područjima, koja su bogate lekovitim i aromatičnim biljem. Tokom zime, ovce se hrane senom i malim procentom žitarica, pretežno lokalnog uzgoja (do 5%). Analiza VC Sjeničke jagnjetine pokazala je da visoka reputacija tri međusobno povezana VC još nije valorizovana. Slabe veze između proizvođača i odsustvo funkcionalnih grupa stvaraju prostor za posrednike, koji dodatnu vrednost iznose van regiona. Skraćivanje VC-a bi ih isključilo, što je prvi korak za vraćanje dodate vrednosti regionu. Različite inicijative i projekti zajednice koji povezuju ruralni razvoj i dodaju vrednost proizvodima, doprineli bi poboljšanju VC. Inovacije (inovativna upotreba vune, centri za priplod, IT rešenja, itd.), stvaranje specijalizovanih grupa proizvođača, posebno ciljane i prilagođene marketinške strategije, mogle bi doneti novu snagu i efektivnost trenutnim VC-ovima. Fokus treba da bude na podršci mladim ljudima koji još uvek ostaju u ovoj oblasti.

16. Bee pasture for honey production in Slovak Carpathian Mountains

Honey from Slovak mountain areas sold directly from the beekeeper is a highly appreciated product by local and other Slovak consumers. This product, as well as the way it is produced and sold, contributes to rural incomes, fulfills a "farm-to-fork" vision, builds trust between producers and consumers, and makes rural mountain areas more attractive to visitors. Like other areas, the Slovak mountains are also affected by climate change. To this are added lifestyle changes related to demographic and land-use changes. Preliminary results of the MOVING H2020 project, obtained by social scientific methods, confirm that beekeepers and other relevant actors perceive the significant impact of these changes on the quality

of bee grazing. Factors such as drought, rising average temperature, abnormal temperature fluctuations, and extremes in heavy rains and heat waves are perceived as the main consequences of climate change. Consequently, the bee pasture biodiversity is negatively impacted, and plant composition can change and affect pollen and nectar plants' flowering period and duration. The actors of honey value chain agree that the land management practices impact bee health. The nature friendly management in agriculture and forests are favourable not only for honey production but also for protection of bees as essential pollinators in the landscape.

In this context, results reveal that it is crucial to support the maintenance of mountain pastures and meadows, adapt agrotechnical practices suitable for bee grazing, avoid pesticide use in agriculture, and keep autochthonous flowering species in rural gardens.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Slovak Carpathian mountains</p>
<p>Country</p> <p>Slovakia</p>
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Native language

Produkcia medu v slovenských horských oblastiach

Med zo slovenských horských oblastí predávaný priamo od včelára je vysoko oceňovaný produkt lokálnymi aj celoslovenskými spotrebiteľmi. Tento produkt ako aj spôsob jeho produkcie a predaja prispieva k príjmom na vidieku, naplňuje víziu "z farmy na stôl", prispieva k budovaniu dôvery medzi producentmi a spotrebiteľmi a v neposlednom rade prispieva k zatraktívňovaniu horských vidieckych oblastí pre návštevníkov. Podobne ako iné oblasti, aj slovenské horské oblasti sú ovplyvnené klimatickými zmenami. K tomu sa pridávajú aj zmeny životného štýlu, ktoré súvisia s demografickými zmenami a zmenami využitia krajiny. Predbežné výsledky projektu MOVING H2020, získané pomocou sociálnych vedeckých metód potvrdzujú, že včelári a ďalší relevantní aktéri vnímajú výrazný vplyv spomínaných zmien na kvalitu včelej pastvy. Faktory ako sucho, zvyšovanie priemernej teploty, neprirodzené teplotné výkyvy, extrémny vo forme silných dažďov a teplotných vln sú vnímané ako hlavné dôsledky klimatických zmien, ktoré znižujú biodiverzitu včelej pastvy, menia rastlinné zloženie, a ovplyvňujú aj obdobie a dĺžku kvitnutia peľodárnych a nektárodárnych rastlín. Aktéri sa zhodujú aj v tom, že spôsob obhospodarovania krajiny ako opúšťanie pasienkov, agrotechnické postupy nezohľadňujúce vhodnosť pre včeliu pastvu, využívanie pesticídov v poľnohospodárstve, zmena úžitkových záhrad na okrasné s malým množstvom pôvodných kvitnúcich druhov, to všetko má nepriaznivý vplyv na včeliu pastvu a s tým súvisiace zdravie včiel nielen ako producentov ale aj ako dôležitých opel'ovačov v krajine.

17. Making mountain olive groves resilient

Mountain olive groves represent a high percentage of European olive groves. In Andalusia, Europe's main olive oil-producing region, they account for a quarter of the total. The area has many common problems threatening its survival such as low productivity, difficult mechanisation, and high production costs. At the same time, they are crops that provide ecosystem services.

This symbiosis is very notable in the case of olive groves located in protected natural areas such as the Sierras Subbéticas Cordobesas. This is where ADEGUA (<https://adegua.com>), within the MOVING project, analyses the value chain of organic olive oil produced in these mountains, considering this production system as a strategy that combines a commitment to conservation with the valorisation of the product.

Some solutions are proving to be valuable alternatives to solve some of the main problems that this type of management entails. On the one hand, collaboration between livestock farmers and olive growers to graze flocks of sheep during the spring, clearing the pasture and fertilising the soil at the same time. On the other hand, promoting the reuse of by-products such as olive leaves for incorporation into the soil and using the alperujo (a by-product of the extraction process) to make compost and contribute to the soil. Finally, the design of cooperation schemes between the administration of the Natural Park and the small owners of these olive groves, providing mutual support linked to the role played by this type of management in combating erosion and preventing fires.

MOVING Reference Region Betic Systems
Country Spain
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More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/betic-systems-spain/

Native language

Haciendo resilientes los olivares de montaña

Los olivares de montaña representan un porcentaje elevado del olivar europeo. En Andalucía, la principal región europea productora de aceite de oliva, suponen una cuarta parte del olivar. La zona presenta muchos problemas en común que amenazan su continuidad, tales como escasa productividad, difícil mecanización y altos costes de producción. En paralelo se trata de cultivos que prestan beneficiosos servicios ecosistémicos.

Esta simbiosis es muy notable en el caso de olivares situados en espacios naturales protegidos como ocurre en las Sierras Subbéticas Cordobesas. Es aquí donde ADEGUA (<https://adegua.com>) dentro del proyecto MOVING analiza la cadena de valor del aceite de oliva ecológico producido en estas montañas considerando este sistema de producción como una estrategia que combina un compromiso de conservación con la valorización del producto.

Algunas soluciones se están mostrando como alternativas útiles para resolver algunos de los principales problemas que este tipo de manejo conlleva. Por un lado, la colaboración entre ganaderos y agricultores para hacer que rebaños de ovejas pasten durante la primavera, desbrozando el pasto a la vez que fertilizando el suelo. Por otro, promoviendo la reutilización de sub-productos como la hoja para su incorporación a los suelos, del mismo modo que utilizar el alperujo (sub-producto del proceso de extracción) para la elaboración del compost y aportación al suelo. Por último, el diseño de fórmulas de cooperación entre la administración del Parque Natural y los pequeños propietarios de estos olivares intercambiando compromisos y ayudas por el papel de lucha contra la erosión y prevención de incendios que este tipo de manejo desempeña.

18. The taste of dehesa: Los Pedroches PDO Iberian Ham (Jamón Ibérico) value chain

Dehesa is a unique multi-functional agroforestry system of the Iberian Peninsula, covering 2.3 million hectares in Spain where Iberian ham (Jamón Ibérico) is produced. Traditional Iberian pig grazing is one of the key dehesa activities and Iberian ham is the value chain with the highest value-added final product (up to 242 euros/kg). Traditional practices and know-how shape this production. In order to obtain a final high-quality product, three conditions are required: 1) specific Iberian pig breed, 2) pigs freely grazed in the dehesa, and 3) pigs fed with acorns (nuts from holm oaks) and pastures. Such features highly contribute to the resilience and sustainability of the dehesa and the related territories. In order to ensure the traceability and the high-quality of the Iberian ham value chain, the Iberian ham Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) Los Pedroches has been created, at Los Pedroches region, in the Sierra Morena Mountains in the Province of Cordoba (Andalusia, Spain). This PDO has been a key opportunity for the valorisation of the natural, social, and cultural capitals of the territory. The challenge is how to support this value chain, which represents a small niche in the national ham production, and it is also threatened by challenges such as climate change. Some practical recommendations are: 1) professionalisation of the value chain (skill upgrading), 2) better marketing differentiation strategies, 3) consumer awareness of the value of the dehesa and the qualities of the Iberian ham, 4) public infrastructures (slaughterhouse), 5) tree rejuvenation, and 5) updated policies and governance approaches for the holistic and integrated management of the dehesa and the value chain.

<p style="text-align: center;">MOVING Reference Region</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Sierra Morena</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Country</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Spain</p>
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Native language

El sabor de la dehesa: Cadena de valor de jamón Ibérico DOP Los Pedroches

La dehesa es un sistema agroforestal multifuncional único en la Península Ibérica, que abarca 2,3 millones de hectáreas en España y en el que se produce el jamón ibérico. La crianza tradicional del cerdo ibérico es una de las actividades clave de la dehesa y el jamón ibérico la cadena de valor de mayor valor añadido (hasta 242 euros/kg). Las prácticas y el saber hacer tradicionales conforman esta producción. Para obtener un jamón ibérico de alta calidad se requieren tres condiciones: 1) raza específica de cerdo ibérico, 2) crecer en libertad en la dehesa, y 3) alimentarse de bellota y pastos. Esta forma de producción contribuye, en gran medida, a la resiliencia y sostenibilidad de la dehesa y el territorio en el que se inserta. Para garantizar la trazabilidad y la calidad de la cadena de valor del jamón ibérico se ha creado la Denominación de Origen Protegida (DOP) Jamón Ibérico Los Pedroches, en la Sierra Morena Cordobesa (Andalucía, España). Esta DOP ha sido una oportunidad clave para la puesta en valor de los capitales naturales, sociales y culturales en la comarca de Los Pedroches. Un reto importante del territorio es cómo apoyar a esta cadena de valor, que representa un pequeño nicho en la producción nacional de jamón, y que además está amenazada por factores como el cambio climático. Algunas recomendaciones prácticas son: 1) la profesionalización de la cadena de valor, 2) mejores estrategias de diferenciación en la comercialización, 3) la concienciación de los consumidores sobre el valor de la dehesa y las cualidades del jamón Ibérico, 4) dotar de infraestructuras como mataderos, 5) rejuvenecimiento de los árboles, y 6) contar con políticas adecuadas y enfoques de gobernanza que permitan la gestión integrada de la dehesa y de esta cadena de valor.

19. Early development of a mountain wine value chain: vigneron from Huesca, Pyrenees

The region of Hoya de Huesca is a transition zone between the pre-Pyrenean mountains and the Ebro valley. About half of the province's surface is flat and occupied by intensive arable crops, mainly cereals, and animal breeding. A newly reborn mountain wine value chain is now in its first development stages. It is linked to the landscape of Ayerbe/ Loarre, the Pyrenees foothills, north-west of Huesca. Progressive depopulation and labour shortage have pushed farmers towards a dominant grain monoculture system, though not competitive at national and global scale. Vineyards were progressively abandoned to make room for less demanding crops. Recently, some farmers decided to replant vineyards in the

area, taking advantage of climate change. Viticulture and wine production remain marginal for Huesca, but it is the only farming activity that grants sufficient income to farmers and may help the social revival of villages currently experiencing depopulation. The vineyards of the region are included in the GI Ribera del Gállego/Cinco Villas, representing about 4% of the Aragon vineyards, total surface of each is over 30.000 ha. The peculiarity of this reborn wine region is the absence of external investors, while the initiative relays on few entrepreneurial local or neo-rural producers, engaged in regaining native varieties to cultivation, gathering actors along the entire value chain, setting synergies with tourism and creating quality brands for the development of the whole territory. The community interaction is a main feature of the value chain. The main risks for viticulture in the area, in coming decades, are linked to further temperatures increase, drought, and physical soil degradation.

<p style="text-align: center;">MOVING Reference Region</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Spanish Pyrenees</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Country</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Spain</p>
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Native language

Desarrollo preliminar de una cadena de valor del vino de montaña: vigneronos de Huesca, Pirineos

La región de la Hoya de Huesca es una zona de transición entre las montañas prepirenaicas y el valle del Ebro. Aproximadamente la mitad de la superficie de la provincia es llana y está ocupada por cultivos herbáceos intensivos y por la ganadería. La cadena de valor del vino de montaña, recién renacida, se encuentra en sus primeras fases de desarrollo. Está vinculada al paisaje de Ayerbe/ Loarre, las estribaciones de los Pirineos, al noroeste de Huesca. La despoblación progresiva y la escasez de mano de obra han empujado a los agricultores hacia un sistema de monocultivo de cereales dominante, aunque no competitivo a escala nacional y mundial. Los viñedos se fueron abandonados para dejar espacio a cultivos menos exigentes. Recientemente, algunos agricultores han decidido replantar viñedos en la zona, aprovechando el cambio climático. La producción de vino sigue siendo marginal para Huesca, pero es la única actividad agrícola que garantiza una renta suficiente a los agricultores y puede ayudar a la reactivación social de los pueblos. Los viñedos de la region están incluidos en la IGP Ribera del Gállego/Cinco Villas, representando cerca del 4% del viñedo aragonés, cuya superficie total supera las 30.000 ha. La peculiaridad de esta renacida zona vitivinícola es la ausencia de inversores externos: la iniciativa se apoya en unos pocos productores locales, reuniendo a los actores a lo largo de toda la cadena de valor, estableciendo sinergias con el turismo y creando marcas de calidad para el desarrollo del territorio. La interacción comunitaria es la característica principal de la cadena de valor. Los principales riesgos para la viticultura de la zona están relacionados con el aumento de las temperaturas, la sequía y la degradación física del suelo.

20. A future-oriented case of diversifying mountain farming through cooperative organic grain production

The value chain of organic mountain grain in the canton of Grisons is managed by the Gran Alpin cooperative, which is the focus of our study. Arable farming has become rare in the mountains, while livestock rearing remains the predominant production system. However, Gran Alpin provides a prime example of the diversification of traditional farming practices at high altitudes. This diversification enhances the ecological, socio-cultural and economic value of the region in a way that is enriching for the farmers and many actors. By focusing on organic certification, high quality and diversity of grain varieties (barley, rye, oat, buckwheat...), market demand for Gran Alpin products exceeds current production.

Our research to date has shown that availability of site-appropriate seeds, management of the value chain and processing facilities, and current support for livestock production in the region are the main factors holding back grain production on farms. The reasons for success so far have been identified as the cooperative's drive, partnerships with local processors and retailers, and premium pricing through organic and regional branding. The challenges of marketing are taken on by the cooperative on behalf of the farmers, which reduces the effort needed to increase grain production or even start it in the first place. We believe that this value chain shows that plant-based value chains in the mountains combined with livestock farming are visionary and that innovative cooperative projects can accelerate development by combining traditional approaches reinvented for current trends.

MOVING Reference Region
Swiss Alps
Country Switzerland
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More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/swiss-alps-switzerland/

Native language

Ein zukunftsweisendes Beispiel für die Diversifizierung der Berglandwirtschaft durch genossenschaftliche bio-Getreideproduktion

Die Graubündner Bio-Berggetreide-Wertschöpfungskette wird von der Genossenschaft Gran Alpin verwaltet, die im Mittelpunkt unserer Studie steht. Der Bergackerbau ist selten geworden, während die Viehwirtschaft das vorherrschende Produktionssystem bleibt. Gran Alpin präsentiert hier eine Diversifizierung traditioneller berglandwirtschaftlicher Praktiken. Diese steigert den ökologischen, soziokulturellen und wirtschaftlichen Wert der Region und ist nicht zuletzt für die Landwirtschaft eine Bereicherung. Durch den Fokus auf Bio-Zertifizierung und hohe Qualität der vielfältigen Getreidesorten übersteigt die Marktnachfrage nach Gran Alpin-Produkten die derzeitige Produktion. Unsere bisherigen Untersuchungen haben gezeigt, dass die Verfügbarkeit von standortgerechtem Saatgut, das Management der Wertschöpfungskette und der Verarbeitungsanlagen sowie die derzeitige Unterstützung der Viehwirtschaft in der Region die wichtigsten Faktoren sind, die die Getreideproduktion hindern. Als Gründe für den bisherigen Erfolg wurden die Initiative der Genossenschaft, Partnerschaften mit lokalen Verarbeitern und Einzelhändlern sowie Premium-Preise durch Branding genannt. Die Herausforderungen der Vermarktung werden von Gran Alpin übernommen, was eine Steigerung oder überhaupt ein Einstieg in die Getreideproduktion vereinfachen kann. Wir glauben, dass dieses Beispiel zeigt, dass pflanzliche Wertschöpfungsketten in den Bergen in Kombination mit der Viehzucht visionär sind und dass innovative genossenschaftliche Projekte die Entwicklung beschleunigen können, indem sie traditionelle Ansätze kombinieren und für aktuelle Trends aneignen.

21. The resilience of Tête de Moine Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) value chain

Tête de Moine cheese is made in nine regional dairies in accordance with the PDO specifications. Not less than 70% of the cows' feed ration must originate from the farm or from adjoining communal pastures on which the cattle must be kept for at least 120 days. Farmers, cheesemakers and ripening experts work with the most modern equipment, but in accordance with traditional craftsmanship. For exemple: silage feed is prohibited. The ripening period begins after the salt-water bath, when the cheese loaves are stored for at least 75 days on spruce boards in the PDO geographical area, during which time they are regularly tended by automated machines. A procedure known as "taxation" (quality control and approval) is carried out every month in the cellars, during which the cheese is evaluated in accord to strict criteria. Tête de Moine PDO is not cut, but pared into "rosettes" with a Girolle or a similar device. This is an important innovation which favoured the selling of the cheese: between the introduction of the Girolle in 1982 and the creation of the PDO in 2001 the volumes increase from 20 to 1600 tons. This trend will probably continue as there is still a significant pool of milk production in the PDO region. Nevertheless, grass can be vulnerable to climate change and producers are aware that the value chain will have to cope with these constraints and also with a strong societal demand for a higher proportion of grass in the cows' ration. Among the strategies identified to foster resilience: to keep the professions (breeder, cheesemaker) attractive to new generations; to promote fodder and water storage; to strengthen the link with local resources, particularly wooded pastures; to develop synergies with other sectors, such as tourism and culture.

MOVING Reference Region
Swiss Jura
Country Switzerland
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More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/swiss-jura-switzerland/

Native language

La résilience de la chaîne de valeur de l'Appellation d'Origine Protégée (AOP) Tête de Moine

Le fromage Tête de Moine est produit dans neuf fromageries, conformément au cahier des charges de l'AOP. 70% de la ration des vaches doit provenir de l'exploitation ou des pâturages communaux attenants sur lesquels les bovins doivent être gardés pendant au moins 120 jours. Agriculteurs, fromagers et affineurs travaillent avec des équipements modernes, tout en respectant les traditions. Par exemple: l'ensilage est interdit. L'affinage s'effectue pendant au moins 75 jours sur des planches d'épicéa; pendant ce temps les fromages sont régulièrement entretenus par des robots de soins. Une procédure de "taxation" (contrôle de la qualité) est effectuée chaque mois dans les caves, pour évaluer le fromage selon des critères stricts.

La Tête de Moine AOP est découpée en rosettes à l'aide d'une Girolle ou d'un dispositif similaire. C'est une innovation importante qui a favorisé les ventes: entre l'introduction de la Girolle en 1982 et la création de l'AOP en 2001, les volumes sont passés de 20 à 1600 tonnes. Cette tendance va probablement se poursuivre car il existe encore un important bassin de production laitière dans l'aire de l'AOP. Néanmoins, l'herbe peut être vulnérable au changement climatique et les producteurs sont conscients que la chaîne de valeur devra faire face à ces contraintes mais aussi à une forte demande sociétale pour une plus grande part d'herbe dans la ration des vaches. Parmi les stratégies identifiées pour favoriser la résilience: maintenir l'attractivité des métiers (éleveur, fromager) pour les nouvelles générations; favoriser le stockage de fourrage et d'eau ; renforcer le lien avec les ressources locales, notamment les pâturages boisés ; développer des synergies avec d'autres secteurs, comme le tourisme et la culture.

22. The Sustainability of Highland Greenhouse Tomato Cultivation in Elmalı / Beydaglari

Reference region is Beydaglari which has two towns, Elmalı and Korkuteli. Elmalı is a town with largest greenhouses tomato production. Greenhouse tomato cultivation has been carried out in Elmalı since 2000. The suitability of climatic conditions such as daylight intensity and temperatures has led to the development of greenhouse cultivation. The greenhouse tomato cultivation starts in Beydaglari when the production ends in the regions with the lower altitudes. Thus, domestic and export demands can be met throughout the year. The greenhouse tomato cultivation is important for the local economy. In the current situation, the fact that greenhouse tomato production is profitable enhances farmers' interest in greenhouse cultivation. In the region, investments in greenhouse agriculture are expanding. The highland greenhouse cultivation is important in the region, as it promotes effective use of regional sources, increases the income of people, and creates employment, thus reduces migration from rural areas. The region is vulnerable to problems such as drought due to climate change. Irrigation problems have started in the region and are expected to increase in the near future. The availability of irrigation is critical for the greenhouse tomato production. Necessary measures against the negative effects of climate change have to be taken. Also, high input costs, crop diseases and labour shortages are the other challenges for greenhouse tomato production. MOVING project will help to raise awareness about economic, social and environmental challenges which affect the sustainability of greenhouse production and will develop policies.

MOVING Reference Region Beydaglari
Country Turkey
Authors Murat Yercan, Hakan Adanacioglu, Duygu Tosun, Filiz Kinikli (EGE)
More info https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/beydaglari-turkey/

Native language

Elmalı-Beydağları Yayla Seracılığında Domates Tarımının Sürdürülebilirliği

Referans bölgesi olarak seçilen Beydağları, Elmalı ve Korkuteli olmak üzere iki önemli yerleşim yerine sahiptir. Bunların içinden Elmalı domates seracılığının en fazla yapılan bölgesidir. Örtü altı domates yetiştiriciliği Elmalı'da 2000'li yıllardan itibaren yapılmaya başlanmıştır. Işık ve sıcaklık gibi iklim koşullarının uygunluğu örtü altı yetiştiriciliğinin gelişmesine yol açmıştır. Örtü altı üretimi sahil bölgelerinde bittikten sonra yaylalarda başlamaktadır. Böylece yıl boyunca yurtiçi ve yurtdışı talepleri karşılanabilmektedir. Örtü altı domates yetiştiriciliği bölge ekonomisi için önemlidir. Mevcut durumda örtü altı domates üretiminin karlı olması, çiftçilerin örtü altı yetiştiriciliğine olan ilgisini artırmaktadır. Bu da bölgede örtü altı tarımına yönelik yatırımları yaygınlaştırmaktadır. Yayla örtü altı tarımı, bölgesel kaynakların etkin kullanımını teşvik etmesi, halkın gelirini artırması, istihdam yaratması ve dolayısıyla kırsaldan göçü azaltması nedeniyle bölgede önemlidir. Bölge, iklim değişikliğinin etkisiyle kuraklık gibi sorunlarla karşı karşıya kalmaktadır. Bölgede sulama sorunları yaşanmaya başlanmış ve yakın gelecekte de artması beklenmektedir. Örtü altı domates üretimi için sulama suyunun olması oldukça önemlidir. Bu nedenle, iklim değişikliğinin olumsuz etkilerine karşı gerekli tedbirlerin alınması gerekmektedir. Ayrıca, yüksek girdi maliyetleri, hastalık ve zararlılar ve işgücü temini sıkıntısı, örtü altı domates üretiminin önündeki diğer zorluklar arasındadır. MOVING projesi, sera üretiminin sürdürülebilirliğini etkileyen ekonomik, sosyal ve çevresel zorluklar hakkında farkındalık yaratmaya ve politikalar geliştirmeye yardımcı olacaktır.

23. Speyside Malt Whisky

Our Value Chain (VC) is Speyside Malt Whisky. Within the Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) there are 28 distilleries; and Speyside has the largest concentration of Scotland's 130 distilleries. Our MRL falls almost exclusively in Cairngorms National Park (CNP) - the UK's largest National Park. Malt Whisky requires several inputs - natural resources including malted barley and wood for the barrels, as well as mountain sourced water, which is vulnerable to climate change and competition from other sectors; built, economic and human capitals. Scotch Malt Whisky marketing uses symbolic and cultural references to remote and romantic mountain areas. The main mountain VC practices are: production of the inputs –

i.e. water; processing – this has several steps (mash, fermentation, distillation, and maturation for at least 3 years) which mainly takes place within the MRL; distribution and marketing is generally carried out by the head offices of the parent companies and includes global exports; and consumption that takes place globally, but also consumers visit the MRL for whisky tours and festivals. Visiting distilleries as a tourism activity is increasing and has become part of the National Park's strategy for promoting local food and drink tourism. Input actors are diverse; however, the processing and distribution parts of single malt production is highly consolidated with two international corporations dominating in the MRL. Consumption is highly distributed across actor types and spaces. Transport and energy infrastructure actors are important to the VC, and the industry is both highly regulated and protected through its PGI status. The industry is innovative and committed to Net Zero, making it an interesting place-based VC.

<p>MOVING Reference Region</p> <p>Highlands and Islands</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Country</p> <p style="text-align: center;">UK-Scotland</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Authors</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Rachel Creaney, Kirsty Blackstock (The James Hutton Institute)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">More info</p> <p style="text-align: center;">https://www.moving-h2020.eu/reference_regions/highlands-and-islands-uk-scotland/</p>

24. Participatory Theory Building: a citizen-science approach for "grounding" the MOVING conceptual and analytical framework

Inspired by the citizen-science approach, the Participatory Theory Building (PTB) aims at improving the Conceptual and Analytical Framework (CAF) by refining its concepts and grounding them into practice. The PTB advances the CAF so to make it able to describe and interpret the diversity of mountain VCs and assess their contribution to the sustainability and resilience of mountain areas and population. For this co-learning process, two workshops were organised, involving MOVING partners to collect inputs to: i) define the CAF's boundaries, and b) clarify some essential concepts. The feedbacks collected were used to refine the concepts and ground the CAF in the stakeholders' empirical knowledge while strengthening the learning process within the consortium.

MOVING Participatory Theory Building

Authors

Manola Colabianchi, Tarek Allali,
Francesco Felici, Michele Moretti
(University of Pisa)

More info

Deliverable: [D2.1](#) Conceptual and analytical framework (draft)

[Blog article](#): Linking the Value Chain to Socio-Ecological Systems approaches

[Video](#): Understanding MOVING Conceptual and Analytical Framework (CAF)

The most relevant outcomes of the first two PTB exercises pertain the concepts of resilience and sustainability (the CAF must look for analytical procedures combining the systemic approach with the analysis of potential trade-off between them); conducive policy environment (the CAF must consider both the regulatory as well as the implementation of policies); and VCs' specificities. In this regard, the current categorization of 'local' or 'global' is based on i) the amount of value distributed to local actors, and ii) the specificity of local resources used – conceived as territorial capital - and actors in the value chains which depend on the degree of control actors can have on the resource, processes, and governance of the value chain.

Native language

Costruzione di una teoria partecipata: un approccio scienze-società per radicare il quadro Concettuale ed Analitico di MOVING

Ispirato dall'approccio citizen-science, la costruzione di teorie partecipative (TPs) mira a migliorare il quadro Concettuale e Analitico (*Conceptual and Analytical Framework - CAF*) affinandone i concetti e radicandoli nella pratica. La TP fa progredire il CAF rendendolo capace di descrivere la diversità delle catene del valore montane e stimare il loro contributo alla sostenibilità e resilienza delle aree e delle popolazione montane. Per questo processo di co-apprendimento, sono stati organizzati due workshop, coinvolgendo i partner di MOVING per la raccolta di contributi finalizzati a: i) definire i confini del CAF, e b) chiarire alcuni suoi concetti essenziali. I commenti recepiti hanno rifinito i concetti e radicato il CAF nella conoscenza empirica dei partner del consorzio. I risultati più rilevanti dei primi due workshops hanno riguardato i concetti di resilienza e sostenibilità (il CAF deve considerare procedure analitiche che combinino l'approccio sistemico con l'analisi dei potenziali compromessi tra i due concetti); ambiente politico favorevole (il CAF deve considerare i processi di definizione ed implementazione delle politiche); e la specificità delle catene del valore. In tal senso, l'attuale categorizzazione di "locale" o "globale" si basa i) sulla quantità di valore distribuito agli attori locali e ii) sulla specificità delle risorse locali utilizzate - concepite come capitale territoriale - e degli attori nelle catene del valore che dipendono dal grado di influenza che gli attori possono avere sulle risorse, sui processi e sulla governance della catena del valore.

25. Inventory of over 400 European Mountain Value Chains

The Inventory of Mountain Value Chains describes 454 value chains (VCs) and covers all European mountain regions located in the EU Member States and associated countries. It provides a broad overview of the diversity of 'mountain' VCs configurations to analyse the dynamics and interaction of human beings with the geomorphological and biophysical factors that characterise mountain areas (e.g., high altitude, steepness, remoteness, diversity of ecosystems, landscape characteristics). The VCs included are different, there are those based on circular bio-economy processes, ecosystem service provision, innovative governance methods, novel market strategies, and digital innovations, as well as those engaged in the enhancement of local resources based on culture and local knowledge. To develop the inventory, first a list of mountain VCs was made then the VCs were characterized considering (i) local material and non-material assets (e.g., land use, landscape amenities, cultural knowledge) they rely upon, (ii) main human actors managing these resources, (iii) current (predicted) challenges VCs are (will be) confronted with in face of the foreseen climatic, socioeconomic, and demographic trends. According to the participatory approach of the project, the data collection template was tested by three partners. After incorporating the pilot suggestions, each partner involved in the inventory was asked to collect data and information for twenty mountain VCs in their respective countries. The data collected were provided by the partners through a combination of desk analysis and expert opinions.

MOVING Inventory of Mountain Value Chains

Authors

Manola Colabianchi, Tarek Allali,
Francesco Felici, Michele Morett
(University of Pisa)

More info

Deliverable: [D4.1](#) Inventory of Mountain Value Chains

[Blog article](#): Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation patterns

[Infographic](#): Mountains Value Chains Inventory

Native language

Inventario di oltre 400 catene del valore di montagna Europee

L'Inventario delle catene del valore di montagna descrive 454 catene del valore (VC) e copre tutte le regioni montane europee situate negli Stati Membri dell'UE e nei Paesi Associati. L'inventario fornisce un'ampia panoramica della diversità delle configurazioni delle VC "montane" per analizzare le interazioni degli esseri umani con i fattori geomorfologici e biofisici che caratterizzano le aree montane. Le VC incluse sono varie: ci sono quelle basate su processi di bioeconomia circolare, sulla fornitura di servizi ecosistemici, su metodi di governance innovativi, su nuove strategie di mercato e su innovazioni digitali, così come quelle impegnate nella valorizzazione delle risorse locali basate sulla cultura e sulla conoscenza locale. Per sviluppare l'inventario, è stato dapprima stilato un elenco delle VC montane, quindi le VC sono state caratterizzate considerando (i) le risorse materiali e immateriali locali su cui si basano, (ii) i principali attori umani che gestiscono queste risorse, (iii) le sfide attuali (previste) che le VC si trovano (si troveranno) ad affrontare a fronte delle tendenze climatiche, socioeconomiche e demografiche previste. Secondo l'approccio partecipativo del progetto, tre partner hanno testato il modello per la raccolta dei dati. Dopo aver incorporato i suggerimenti dei tests, a ciascun partner coinvolto nell'inventario è stato chiesto di raccogliere dati e informazioni per venti VC di montagna nei rispettivi Paesi. I dati raccolti sono stati forniti dai partner attraverso una combinazione di analisi documentale e pareri di esperti.

26. Farming and Forestry Systems in Mountain Areas

The [23 Reference Regions](#) (RRs) studied in MOVING span over 16 countries, representing different contexts. Although no in depth cross-analysis was made, it is possible to draw some knowledge from the systematization of information about the farming and forestry systems existing in the selected RRs.

MOVING Farming and forestry in mountain areas

Authors

Catarina Esgalhado (University of Évora)

Forests are the dominant land cover across the RRs, and most regions have high to very high tree densities. In many of the RRs there was an increase of the forest cover over the last decade, but the majority had a decrease in tree density. In RRs from southern countries (Sierra Morena, Cordilheira central, Corsica, Crete, Maciço Norte and Betic Systems), forest stands are more scattered and shrublands and grasslands have a bigger expression.

Despite the cultural and local relevance of shepherding and small-scale farming in the RRs, generally, agricultural cover is relatively small at the RR scale. Heterogeneous agricultural areas make most of the agricultural cover, followed by arable land and pasture. Permanent crops are particularly important in Crete and Betic System, whereas the Transdanubian Mountain has the highest cover of arable land.

Mountain regions face similar threats and challenges. However, they have context specific dynamics, that can determine farming and forestry systems. Identifying these processes can provide important intel when designing policy recommendations.

27. Farming and Forestry Systems Susceptibility to Climate Change

The MOVING project identified, selected, and developed a closed set of susceptibility indicators to climate change and related ecological disturbances, as well as, to other drivers of a more socio-economic nature, for each of the 23 Mountain Reference Landscapes (MRLs).

MOVING Farming and forestry systems susceptibility to climate change

Authors

Élia Marques (University of Évora)

This set of susceptibility indicators was mainly based on existing pan-European spatial datasets and includes estimates on bio-climate variables, soil loss (present and future), rainfall erosivity (present and future), agricultural abandonment (future), wind erosion (present) and forest disturbance (past), among others.

All indicators available at each of the 23 MRLs were collected and presented to the regional partners, for them to choose the most relevant to their vulnerability model, based on information gathered from local actors.

This work showed, for example, large areas with high risk of agricultural abandonment (2030) in MRLs such as Austrian Alps, Sumava – Cesky Les, Drôme Valley, Northern Apennines and Southern Romanian Carpathian Mountains. It also revealed high levels of soil erosion, in the present, in some areas of Betic Systems and Cordilheira Central MRLs, among others. Regarding, rainfall erosivity, the data showed that in MRLs such as Maciço Noroeste, Stara Planina and Swiss Alps there are areas where it is expected to increase substantially, between the present and 2050. This analysis also exposed that some areas within Cordilheira Central and Slovak Carpathian Mountains MRLs have suffered from high forest disturbance severity, in the recent past.

Although the output of this work is not reported in any Deliverable, it was essential to support subsequent tasks of the project and will also play a key role in upcoming analysis.

Native language

Susceptibilidade dos sistemas agrícolas e florestais às alterações climáticas

O MOVING identificou, selecionou e desenvolveu um conjunto de indicadores de suscetibilidade às alterações climáticas e a perturbações ecológicas relacionadas, bem como a outros fatores de natureza mais socioeconómica, para cada uma das 23 Paisagens de Montanha de Referência (PMR).

Este conjunto de indicadores de suscetibilidade é baseado, sobretudo, em dados espaciais pan-europeus pré-existent e inclui estimativas de variáveis bioclimáticas, perda de solo (presente e futura), erosividade da chuva (presente e futura), abandono de terra (futuro), erosão eólica (presente) e perturbação florestal (passado), entre outros.

Todos os indicadores disponíveis em cada uma das 23 PMR foram reunidos e apresentados aos parceiros regionais, para que seleccionassem os mais relevantes para seu modelo de vulnerabilidade, com base nas informações recolhidas junto aos atores locais.

Este trabalho mostrou, por exemplo, grandes áreas com alto risco de abandono agrícola (2030) em PMR como os Alpes Austríacos, Sumava – Cesky Les, Vale Drôme e Apeninos do Norte. Também revelou altos níveis de erosão do solo, no presente, em algumas áreas das PMR dos Sistemas Béticos e da Cordilheira Central, entre outros. Em relação à erosividade das chuvas, os dados mostraram que em PMR como o Maciço Noroeste, Stara Planina e Alpes Suíços existem áreas onde se espera um aumento substancial, até 2050. Esta análise também revelou que algumas áreas dentro das PMR da Cordilheira Central e dos Montes Cárpatos Eslovacos sofreram perturbações florestais de alta severidade, no passado recente.

Embora o resultado deste trabalho não seja apresentado em nenhum relatório, foi essencial para apoiar as tarefas subsequentes e desempenhará um papel importante em análises futuras.

28. Mapping of mountain areas vulnerability

MOVING project produced Spatial Vulnerability Matrices (SVMs) for the Land Use Systems (LUSs) supporting the focal Value Chains (VCs) in each of the 23 Mountain Reference Landscapes (MRLs). Each regional MOVING team built its SVM from data collection and its own informed assessment, based on the contextualized knowledge gathered in different moments of interaction with local actors and the narratives expressed by them.

MOVING Mapping of mountain areas vulnerability

Authors

Élia Marques (University of Évora)

Each SVM defines different levels of vulnerability of the respective LUS to drivers of change (related to climate or others) in relation to spatial explicit factors. Some of these SVMs allowed us to build Vulnerability Maps within the respective MRL. The objective was to identify the spatial distribution of the vulnerability to relevant drivers, so that information on adaptation mechanisms can be more targeted, in a later phase of the project.

For example, at Swiss Jura MRL the focal value chain is Tête de Moine PDO cheese, which relies on permanent pastures. At areas of with very low tree cover density and low elevation this LUS was considered highly vulnerable to the drivers of precipitation, temperature, and extreme events. At this MRL, most permanent pastures (58%) were classified with a medium vulnerability level. At Austrian Alps MRL, the focal value chain is lamb production, which also relies on permanent pastures. At areas with south exposition and slopes above 20%, permanent pastures vulnerability to aridity, temperature and extreme weather was considered very high. In total, 29% of permanent pastures are in this class.

These and other outputs of this work can be consulted in Deliverable 3.2.: Land use systems vulnerability matrixes and vulnerability maps for the 23 reference regions (González-Moreno et al., 2022).

Native language

Mapeamento da vulnerabilidade das áreas de montanha

O projeto MOVING produziu Matrizes de Vulnerabilidade Espacial (MVE) para os sistemas de uso do solo (SUS) dos quais dependem as Cadeias de Valor (CV) focais em cada uma das 23 Paisagens de Montanha de Referência (PMR). Cada parceiro regional construiu a sua MVE a partir da recolha de dados e de uma avaliação informada própria, com base no conhecimento adquirido nos diferentes momentos de interação com os atores locais e nas suas narrativas.

Cada MVE expressa diferentes níveis de vulnerabilidade do LUS respetivo a fatores de mudança (relacionados com clima ou outros) em relação a fatores espaciais explícitos. Algumas dessas MVE permitiram a construção Mapas de Vulnerabilidade para a PMR respetiva. O objetivo consistiu em identificar a distribuição espacial da vulnerabilidade a fatores relevantes, para que a informação sobre os mecanismos de adaptação possa ser mais direcionada, numa fase posterior do projeto.

Por exemplo, na PMR dos Montes Jura suíços a CV focal é o queijo Tête de Moine DOP que depende de pastagens permanentes. Em áreas com densidade de cobertura arbórea muito baixa e de baixa altitude, este SUS foi considerado altamente vulnerável à precipitação, temperatura e eventos extremos. Nesta PMR, a maioria das pastagens permanentes (58%) foi classificada com nível médio de vulnerabilidade. Por outro lado, na PMR dos Alpes austríacos, a CV focal é a produção de cordeiro, que também depende de pastagens permanentes. Em áreas com exposição sul e declives superiores a 20%, a vulnerabilidade das pastagens permanentes à aridez, temperatura e clima extremo foi considerada muito alta. No total, 29% das pastagens permanentes estão nesta classe.

Os resultados deste trabalho são apresentados no Deliverable 3.2. (González-Moreno et al., 2022).

29. Story Map Building and Visualising Tool for Science and Society

In the MOVING H2020 project, National Research Council of Italy (CNR) designed, developed, and released an online tool - the Story Map Building and Visualising Tool (SMBVT) - that allows users to create story maps within a collaborative environment and a usable Web interface. Story maps are computer science realizations of narratives based on maps, which are accessible through many digital

devices (e.g., PCs, tablets, smartphones, interactive displays). Technically speaking, the advantages of SMBVT are that it is entirely open-source and has been made available on a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) in the MOVING portal, as a free-to-use online solution accessible after registration. Furthermore, it builds up a user-shared semantic knowledge base that automatically interconnects all stories and seamlessly enables collaborative story building. Finally, it was integrated with the MOVING portal, which is based on the D4Science e-Infrastructure, to enable data and information sharing within the MOVING community and add multi-tenancy, multi-user, security, and access-control facilities. From a user's point of view, the tool supports both narrators who want to create a story map about a specific value chain and users who want to consume its content. The main advantage of using story maps is that these online interactive maps enriched with text, pictures, videos, data, and other multimedia information can tell stories over the territories' value chain while representing the life, emotions, reality, fiction, legends, and expectations associated with the described territories.

MOVING Story Map Building and Visualising Tool for Science and Society

Authors

Valentina Bartalesi, Emanuele Lenzi,
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30. Creating a Community of Practice on Mountain Areas

The overall objective of [MOVING](#) (MOUNTAIN Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth) Horizon 2020 project is to build capacities and co-develop relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of new or upgraded and upscaled value chains that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas. This is being done through a bottom-up participatory process with value chain actors, regional and European stakeholders and policy-makers.

MOVING Community of Practice (CoP)
Authors Blanca Casares (AEIDL, European Association for Innovation in Local Development)

A core feature of the project is the creation and animation of its [Community of Practice](#) (CoP).

The MOVING CoP is understood as a European-wide Science-Society-Policy interface to engage stakeholders around resilience to climate change, and other threats, of mountain value chains.

The conceptualisation of the MOVING CoP is transferred into practice through the creation of Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), that provide the space for interaction, exchange and learning with stakeholders of the community at all territorial levels (regional and European). The CoP is built on:

- 23 regional MAPs, established in the [23 Reference Regions](#);
- 1 [EU MAP](#);
- External actors.

The objectives of the MOVING CoP are:

- to bring together a community that contributes to the co-creation and validation of key research outputs and results delivered by MOVING;
- to foster the exchange of knowledge and experience that enhances joint learning and expertise on mountain value chains;
- to build a long-lasting community.

So far the CoP consists of more than 500 actors in the regional MAPs and 50 members in the EU MAP.

Interested in becoming part of the EU MAP? Join [here](#).

31. Building a shared understanding of Mountain Value Chains

Within the H2020 MOVING project, we are analysing mountain value chains across 23 different mountain locations. Using an approach that builds on the Value Chain Analysis for Development (VCA4D), we illustrate how taking this type of extended value chain can provide a fresh perspective on mountain rural development. A value chain connects the stages by which values (economic, environmental and socio-cultural) are added as raw materials become products, that are processed, distributed and marketed and finally consumed. The values that are added depend on harnessing the capitals or assets of the mountain locations - these can be natural resources, local know-how or community spirit. This value chain analysis illustrates how mountain assets are the foundation for regional or national economic sectors. Very often, the later value chain practices take place a long way from the mountains, which can dilute the economic value for producers, but also reduce the ability of local people to influence how the products are developed or the degree to which their mountain origins are recognised by consumers. In the H2020 MOVING project, the participation of mountain producers in understanding the value chain is essential, due to their local knowledge of how mountain assets are involved and what benefits arise. Often statistics and publications are not available for the specific mountain value chain activities, so insights from local experts is the best sources of evidence. The value chain approach can connect these producers to other actors involved in the value chain outside mountain areas, helping mountain people to have a voice in global value chains and/or to identify ways to relocalise other parts of the value chain to retain more value in mountain areas.

<p>MOVING Community of Practice (CoP)</p>
<p>Authors Kirsty Blackstock, Sharon Flanigan, Rachel Creaney (The James Hutton Institute)</p>